

Supplementary material

Adverse Reactions with VEGF Inhibitors in Combination with NSAIDs:

Disproportionality Analysis Using JADRE and FAERS

Kazuki Saito¹, Satoru Nihei^{1,2}, Junichi Asaka^{1,2}, Kenzo Kudo^{1,2}

¹Department of Pharmacy, Iwate Medical University Hospital, Iwate, Japan;

²Division of Clinical Pharmaceutics and Pharmacy Practice, Department of Clinical Pharmacy, School of Pharmacy, Iwate Medical University, Iwate, Japan;

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Table S1. The READUS-PV checklist

Section and topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
Title			
	1a	If disproportionality analyses are a prominent component of the published study, the study should be identified as a “disproportionality analysis”. The type of data and name of the database(s) should be specified.	Title
	1b	Report the name of adverse event(s) and/or drug(s) under study, when applicable.	Title
Introduction			
Background	2a	Describe the drug(s) and its utilization, the nature of the adverse event(s) under study and its frequency, and the existing knowledge on the drug-event combination.	Page 3
	2b	Specify the rationale for performing the analysis, e.g., as part of routine pharmacovigilance, to investigate an overall safety profile, or to assess a pre-specified hypothesis.	Page 4
	2c	Explain why ICSR databases and disproportionality analysis are suitable to fill the knowledge gap.	Page 4
Objectives	3	State specific objectives, identifying the adverse event(s), the drug(s), and the reference group, including any pre-specified hypothesis, if applicable.	Page 4
Methods			
Study design	4a	Identify the study (i.e., “disproportionality analysis”) and the type of data used (e.g., “individual case safety reports”).	Page 5
	4b	Provide an outline of the entire study design, including primary and sensitivity analyses performed, and other designs such as case-by-case analysis or literature review.	Page 5 and Fig 1
Data description, access, and pre-	5a	Specify the name of the database(s), the database(s) custodian, and the coverage. Specify the type/number of	Page 5

processing		drugs included within the database and the thesaurus, taxonomies, or ontologies used for coding drugs and events.	
	5b	Specify the extraction dates and describe and justify all choices used for data pre-processing, including any data transformation or exclusion, if appropriate.	Page 6
Variables definition	6a	Describe the study population, including any restriction.	Page 5
	6b	Describe the nature and the meaning of key variables assessed in the work.	Page 6
	6c	Specify and justify any grouping of drugs or events. For drugs, specify and justify whether active ingredients/trade names/salts were considered and/or the selected role.	Page 6
	6d	Describe any additional data source used, the type of data, and how they interact with ICSRs.	None
Statistical methods	7a	Present any descriptive analysis performed, specifying variables investigated, statistical tests, and significance thresholds.	Page 7
	7b	Describe the measure(s) selected for the disproportionality analysis including any threshold used to identify signals of disproportionate reporting. Explain the reason for this choice if applicable.	Page 7
	7c	Clearly describe any sensitivity analysis and any tool to control confounding, including any restriction, subgroup, stratification, adjustment, or interaction.	Page 8
	7d	Specify the variables and methods used for the case-by-case analysis, including any algorithm or criteria used to assess causality, if performed.	None
	7e	Specify any statistical methods used for other data sources.	None
Results			
Participants	8a	Specify the number of individual case safety reports included at each stage, including reasons for exclusion.	Fig 1
	8b	Provide key demographic and clinical characteristics of cases, if possible comparing cases with any appropriate reference	Table S3

		group.	
Disproportionality analysis	9	Present all results including confidence intervals. Present also results of sensitivity analyses, if performed.	Table 2-4 and S4
Case-by-case analysis	10	Present the case-by-case analysis of key variables. Present the causality assessment, if applicable.	None
Discussion			
Key results	11	Discuss key results with reference to study objectives and contextualize them within the current literature and other consulted sources. Clearly discriminate between expected reactions and emerging safety signals.	Page 12
External validity	12a	Discuss the external validity of the results to the general population.	Page 16
	12b	Discuss the potential relevance of results in clinical practice	Page 16
	12c	Propose further study designs if applicable	Page 16
Limitations	13	Present general limitations, making clear that disproportionality analysis alone cannot prove causation or measure incidence, and specific limitations, including confounding and reporting bias and efforts to mitigate them.	Page 15
Declarations			
	14a	Provide the source of funding/sponsorship and the role of the funders/sponsors for the present study and for any original study on which the present article is based.	Page 16
	14b	Clearly identify potential commercial and intellectual conflicts of interest (e.g., link to any drug/event investigated, whether financial, legal action, or software used).	Page 16
	14c	Declare any institutional approval needed or granted in the investigation.	Page 16
	14d	Include a statement on data availability, code availability (including the version of the statistical software used), and protocol registration.	Page 16

Table SIII. STROBE Statement checklist

	Item No	Recommendation	Location where item is reported
Title and abstract	1	(a) Indicate the study's design with a commonly used term in the title or the abstract	Title
		(b) Provide in the abstract an informative and balanced summary of what was done and what was found	Abstract
Introduction			
Background/rationale	2	Explain the scientific background and rationale for the investigation being reported	Page 4
Objectives	3	State specific objectives, including any prespecified hypotheses	Page 4
Methods			
Study design	4	Present key elements of study design early in the paper	Page 4
Setting	5	Describe the setting, locations, and relevant dates, including periods of recruitment, exposure, follow-up, and data collection	Page 5
Participants	6	(a) <i>Cohort study</i> —Give the eligibility criteria, and the sources and methods of selection of participants. Describe methods of follow-up <i>Case-control study</i> —Give the eligibility criteria, and the sources and methods of case ascertainment and control selection. Give the rationale for the choice of cases and controls <i>Cross-sectional study</i> —Give the eligibility criteria, and the sources and methods of selection of participants	Page 8
		(b) <i>Cohort study</i> —For matched studies, give matching criteria and number of exposed and unexposed <i>Case-control study</i> —For matched studies, give matching criteria and the number of controls per case	None

Variables	7	Clearly define all outcomes, exposures, predictors, potential confounders, and effect modifiers. Give diagnostic criteria, if applicable	Page 8
Data sources/ measurement	8*	For each variable of interest, give sources of data and details of methods of assessment (measurement). Describe comparability of assessment methods if there is more than one group	Page 8
Bias	9	Describe any efforts to address potential sources of bias	None
Study size	10	Explain how the study size was arrived at	None
Quantitative variables	11	Explain how quantitative variables were handled in the analyses. If applicable, describe which groupings were chosen and why	None
Statistical methods	12	(a) Describe all statistical methods, including those used to control for confounding	Page 9
		(b) Describe any methods used to examine subgroups and interactions	Page 9
		(c) Explain how missing data were addressed	Page 9
		(d) <i>Cohort study</i> —If applicable, explain how loss to follow-up was addressed <i>Case-control study</i> —If applicable, explain how matching of cases and controls was addressed <i>Cross-sectional study</i> —If applicable, describe analytical methods taking account of sampling strategy	None
		(e) Describe any sensitivity analyses	None

Results			
Participants	13*	(a) Report numbers of individuals at each stage of study—eg numbers potentially eligible, examined for eligibility, confirmed eligible, included in the study, completing follow-up, and analysed	Page 11
		(b) Give reasons for non-participation at each stage	None
		(c) Consider use of a flow diagram	None
Descriptive data	14*	(a) Give characteristics of study participants (eg demographic, clinical, social) and information on exposures and potential confounders	Table S5
		(b) Indicate number of participants with missing data for each variable of interest	Table S5
		(c) <i>Cohort study</i> —Summarise follow-up time (eg, average and total amount)	None
Outcome data	15*	<i>Cohort study</i> —Report numbers of outcome events or summary measures over time	Table S6
		<i>Case-control study</i> —Report numbers in each exposure category, or summary measures of exposure	
		<i>Cross-sectional study</i> —Report numbers of outcome events or summary measures	
Main results	16	(a) Give unadjusted estimates and, if applicable, confounder-adjusted estimates and their precision (eg, 95% confidence interval). Make clear which confounders were adjusted for and why they were included	Table S6 and Page 11
		(b) Report category boundaries when continuous variables were categorized	None
		(c) If relevant, consider translating estimates of relative risk into absolute risk for a meaningful time period	None
Other analyses	17	Report other analyses done—eg analyses of subgroups and interactions, and sensitivity analyses	None
Discussion			
Key results	18	Summarise key results with reference to study objectives	Page 12
Limitations	19	Discuss limitations of the study, taking into account sources of potential bias or imprecision. Discuss both direction and magnitude of any potential bias	Page 16

Interpretation	20	Give a cautious overall interpretation of results considering objectives, limitations, multiplicity of analyses, results from similar studies, and other relevant evidence	Page 16
Generalisability	21	Discuss the generalisability (external validity) of the study results	Page 16
Other information			
Funding	22	Give the source of funding and the role of the funders for the present study and, if applicable, for the original study on which the present article is based	Page 16

Table SIII. Patient characteristics of the two databases in the disproportionality analysis

	JADER (n = 1,509,399)	FAERS (n = 38,610,433)
Gender, n (%)		
Male	721,945 (47.8)	10,082,002 (26.1)
Female	727,610 (48.2)	16,720,608 (43.3)
Unknown	59,844 (4.0)	11,807,823 (30.6)
Age, n (%)		
>10	46,856 (3.1)	677,903 (1.8)
10-19	49,173 (3.3)	1,077,615 (2.8)
20-29	54,071 (3.6)	1,737,046 (4.5)
30-39	79,516 (5.3)	2,490,138 (6.4)
40-49	114,641 (7.6)	3,571,677 (9.3)
50-59	173,086 (11.5)	5,279,602 (13.7)
60-69	289,908 (19.2)	5,624,476 (14.6)
70-79	348,912 (23.1)	4,206,885 (10.9)
80-89	179,160 (11.9)	1,861,607 (4.8)
90-99	27,790 (1.8)	260,195 (0.7)
99<	654 (0.0)	12,785 (0.0)
Unknown	145,632 (9.6)	11,810,504 (30.6)
VEGF inhibitor, n (%)		
Bevacizumab	33,889 (2.2)	284,573 (0.7)
Ramucirumab	6,654 (0.4)	10,031 (0.0)
Aflibercept	2,622 (0.2)	46,717 (0.1)
Axitinib	5,074 (0.3)	32,524 (0.1)
Sunitinib	9,320 (0.6)	154,500 (0.4)
Sorafenib	9,495 (0.6)	90,159 (0.2)
Nintedanib	2,206 (0.1)	63,666 (0.2)
Pazopanib	4,095 (0.3)	70,255 (0.2)
Vandetanib	139 (0.0)	5,773 (0.0)
Regorafenib	3,829 (0.3)	40,088 (0.1)
Lenvatinib	12,308 (0.8)	52,899 (0.1)
Cabozantinib	5,408 (0.4)	69,766 (0.2)
NSAID, n (%)		
Celecoxib	21,383 (1.4)	482,959 (1.3)
Diclofenac	21,327 (1.4)	531,240 (1.4)
Etodolac	5,926 (0.4)	37,180 (0.1)
Ibuprofen	2,570 (0.2)	924,438 (2.4)

Loxoprofen	67,053 (4.4)	68,240 (0.2)
Naproxen	4,184 (0.3)	581,773 (1.5)
AAP, n (%)	46,095 (3.1)	3,094,474 (8.0)

VEGF: vascular endothelial growth factor, NSAID: non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug, AAP: acetaminophen.

Table SIV. Disproportionality analysis using VEGF inhibitors (TKIs or non-TKIs) paired with each NSAID.

		JADER									
		Gastrointestinal perforation					Gastrointestinal haemorrhage				
		Case	Total	PRR ₀₂₅	CSS	Ω ₀₂₅	Case	Total	PRR ₀₂₅	CSS	Ω ₀₂₅
VEGF non-TKIs and	any NSAIDs	582	3402	19.83	2.07	0.94	140	3402	2.28	1.37	-0.20
VEGF non-TKIs and	celecoxib	58	441	12.16	1.07	0.18	17	441	1.56	0.89	-0.78
VEGF non-TKIs and	diclofenac	121	441	27.42	2.48	1.22	13	441	1.11	0.52	-1.47
VEGF non-TKIs and	etodolac	35	130	22.51	1.98	1.06	6	130	1.33	0.65	-1.19
VEGF non-TKIs and	ibuprofen	0	7	-	-	-	0	7	-	-	-
VEGF non-TKIs and	loxoprofen	364	2284	17.75	1.71	0.75	97	2284	2.28	1.34	-0.13
VEGF non-TKIs and	naproxen	38	266	12.35	1.08	0.17	14	266	2.01	1.15	-0.16
VEGF TKI and	any NSAID	125	4187	3.05	1.53	-0.11	197	4187	2.69	1.60	0.03
VEGF TKI and	celecoxib	21	484	3.40	1.62	0.29	14	484	1.11	0.62	-1.29
VEGF TKI and	diclofenac	19	648	2.25	0.73	-0.97	38	648	2.77	1.33	-0.17
VEGF TKI and	etodolac	5	380	0.66	0.29	-2.45	21	380	2.33	1.21	-0.26
VEGF TKI and	ibuprofen	0	24	-	-	-	0	24	-	-	-
VEGF TKI and	loxoprofen	78	2676	2.83	1.39	-0.17	124	2676	2.54	1.47	0.01
VEGF TKI and	naproxen	12	412	1.99	0.70	-0.95	21	412	2.15	1.20	-0.04
		FAERS									
		Gastrointestinal perforation					Gastrointestinal haemorrhage				
		Case	Total	PRR ₀₂₅	CSS	Ω ₀₂₅	Case	Total	PRR ₀₂₅	CSS	Ω ₀₂₅
VEGF non-TKIs and	any NSAIDs	436	17720	12.28	1.45	0.30	193	17720	1.53	0.83	-0.86
VEGF non-TKIs and	celecoxib	42	3402	4.97	0.56	-0.98	27	3402	0.88	0.58	-1.27

VEGF non-TKIs and	diclofenac	104	2231	20.94	2.41	0.91	34	2231	1.76	1.00	-0.59
VEGF non-TKIs and	etodolac	15	319	15.30	1.74	0.56	4	319	0.76	0.35	-2.19
VEGF non-TKIs and	ibuprofen	49	8128	2.49	0.28	-2.03	51	8128	0.77	0.44	-1.80
VEGF non-TKIs and	loxoprofen	209	2349	42.29	4.98	1.78	64	2349	3.45	1.63	0.21
VEGF non-TKIs and	naproxen	36	3092	4.58	0.52	-1.10	29	3092	1.06	0.53	-1.47
VEGF TKI and	any NSAID	174	24002	3.42	1.52	0.18	307	24002	1.86	1.00	-0.60
VEGF TKI and	celecoxib	27	3256	3.10	1.34	0.20	45	3256	1.67	1.08	-0.39
VEGF TKI and	diclofenac	40	4453	3.59	1.56	-0.16	74	4453	2.14	1.22	-0.34
VEGF TKI and	etodolac	1	663	0.12	0.05	-	21	663	3.33	1.59	0.17
VEGF TKI and	ibuprofen	50	9187	2.25	0.97	-0.36	63	9187	0.87	0.49	-1.66
VEGF TKI and	loxoprofen	42	3250	5.21	1.04	-0.43	68	3250	2.67	1.25	-0.20
VEGF TKI and	naproxen	25	5187	1.78	0.76	-0.59	61	5187	1.48	0.74	-1.02

Table SV. Patient characteristics in logistic regression analysis

	JADER (n = 255,177)	FAERS (n = 1,167,941)
Age (%)		
<10/10s/20s/30s/40s/50s/ 60s/70s/80s/90s/<99/unknown	0.6/0.8/0.7/1.8/5.3/12.8/ 26.9/31.3/9.5/0.5/0.0/9.9	[median (IQR)] 64.9 (62.0–70.0)
Gender, n (%)		
Male	141,638 (55.5)	534,847 (45.8)
Female	101,275 (39.7)	549,001 (47.0)
Unknown	12,264 (4.8)	84,093 (7.2)
Cancer type, n (%)		
Hematological	54,406 (21.3)	398,738 (34.1)
Breast	22,393 (8.8)	182,040 (15.6)
Lung	50,106 (19.6)	118,383 (10.1)
Prostate	13,413 (5.3)	92,746 (7.9)
Intestine	25,855 (10.1)	77,107 (6.6)
Kidney	17,740 (7.0)	69,067 (5.9)
Hepatobiliary-pancreas	18,599 (7.3)	44,261 (3.8)
Gynecological	14,724 (5.8)	44,214 (3.8)
Head and neck	6,585 (2.6)	21,774 (1.9)
Gastric	11,515 (4.5)	15,198 (1.3)
Bladder	6,934 (2.7)	9,254 (0.8)
Brain	500 (0.2)	7,941(0.7)
Esophageal	4,235 (1.7)	6,489 (0.6)
Sarcoma	258 (0.1)	4,063 (0.3)
Skin	109 (0.0)	2,757 (0.2)
Other	7,805 (3.1)	73,909 (6.3)
VEGF inhibitor, n (%)	50,337 (19.7)	161,166 (13.8)
NSAID, n (%)	17,612 (6.9)	42,196 (3.6)
AAP, n (%)	7,907 (3.1)	93,067 (8.0)

Age was treated as a categorical variable with 10-year age increments in JADER and as a continuous variable in FAERS, due to different inputs in both databases. VEGF: vascular endothelial growth factor, NSAID: non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug, AAP: acetaminophen

Table SVI. All result of logistic regression analysis

	JADER						FAERS					
	NSAID			AAP			NSAID			AAP		
	cOR	aOR	aOR Interaction									
Gastrointestinal perforation												
	4,946 events						11,303 events					
VEGF	7.33 (6.92–7.78)	7.61 (7.07–8.19)	7.02 (6.49–7.58)	7.33 (6.92–7.78)	7.62 (7.08–8.20)	7.56 (7.02–8.14)	5.36 (5.17–5.57)	4.50 (4.29–4.72)	4.36 (4.15–4.58)	5.36 (5.17–5.57)	4.52 (4.31–4.73)	4.55 (4.34–4.78)
NSAID or AAP	2.63 (2.43–2.84)	2.58 (2.37–2.80)	1.82 (1.57–2.10)	1.14 (0.98–1.33)	1.37 (1.17–1.60)	1.22 (0.96–1.55)	2.24 (2.08–2.40)	2.28 (2.13–2.45)	1.88 (1.70–2.09)	1.15 (1.08–1.22)	1.26 (1.18–1.34)	1.31 (1.20–1.42)
Interaction	-	-	1.74 (1.45–2.07)	-	-	1.24 (0.90–1.70)	-	-	1.49 (1.29–1.72)	-	-	0.91 (0.80–1.04)
Gastrointestinal haemorrhage												
	4,589 events						18,958 events					
VEGF	3.45 (3.25–3.66)	3.03 (2.79–3.30)	2.99 (2.74–3.27)	3.45 (3.25–3.66)	3.06 (2.81–3.32)	3.06 (2.81–3.33)	2.57 (2.49–2.66)	1.90 (1.82–1.99)	1.90 (1.82–1.99)	2.57 (2.49–2.66)	1.90 (1.82–1.99)	1.95 (1.87–2.04)
NSAID or AAP	2.25 (2.07–2.45)	2.22 (2.04–2.42)	2.13 (1.89–2.40)	1.23 (1.06–1.43)	1.34 (1.15–1.57)	1.34 (1.12–1.62)	2.06 (1.94–2.18)	2.08 (1.96–2.20)	2.08 (1.95–2.23)	1.42 (1.36–1.49)	1.50 (1.43–1.57)	1.60 (1.52–1.69)
Interaction	-	-	1.10 (0.92–1.30)	-	-	1.00 (0.71–1.39)	-	-	0.99 (0.87–1.12)	-	-	0.78 (0.70–0.87)
Haemorrhagic CNS vascular conditions												
	1,875 events						13,315 events					

VEGF	2.99 (2.71–3.28)	3.69 (3.24–4.21)	3.77 (3.30–4.32)	2.99 (2.71–3.28)	3.71 (3.25–4.23)	3.71 (3.25–4.23)	1.57 (1.51–1.64)	1.82 (1.71–1.93)	1.80 (1.69–1.91)	1.57 (1.51–1.64)	1.82 (1.71–1.93)	1.81 (1.70–1.92)
NSAID or AAP	1.30 (1.10–1.52)	1.34 (1.14–1.58)	1.47 (1.19–1.83)	1.03 (0.80–1.34)	1.09 (0.84–1.41)	1.09 (0.78–1.49)	1.17 (1.07–1.27)	1.20 (1.10–1.31)	1.15 (1.05–1.27)	1.16 (1.09–1.23)	1.16 (1.09–1.23)	1.15 (1.08–1.23)
Interaction	-	-	0.85 (0.58–1.12)	-	-	0.99 (0.57–1.75)	-	-	1.20 (0.98–1.47)	-	-	1.05 (0.90–1.22)
Embolic and thrombotic events												
	11,494 events						74,322 events					
VEGF	1.84 (1.77–1.92)	2.26 (2.15–2.39)	2.33 (2.20–2.46)	1.84 (1.77–1.92)	2.27 (2.15–2.39)	2.28 (2.16–2.40)	1.33 (1.31–1.36)	1.54 (1.50–1.58)	1.54 (1.50–1.58)	1.33 (1.31–1.36)	1.54 (1.50–1.58)	1.54 (1.50–1.58)
NSAID or AAP	1.18 (1.10–1.27)	1.13 (1.05–1.21)	1.25 (1.15–1.36)	1.07 (0.96–1.19)	1.07 (0.96–1.19)	1.10 (0.98–1.24)	1.21 (1.16–1.25)	1.24 (1.20–1.29)	1.23 (1.18–1.29)	1.23 (1.20–1.26)	1.24 (1.21–1.27)	1.24 (1.20–1.27)
Interaction	-	-	0.72 (0.61–0.84)	-	-	0.84 (0.65–1.10)	-	-	1.05 (0.95–1.15)	-	-	1.00 (0.94–1.08)
Cardiac failure												
	5,177 events						22,688 events					
VEGF	1.13 (1.06–1.21)	1.87 (1.71–2.04)	1.88 (1.72–2.06)	1.13 (1.06–1.21)	1.87 (1.71–2.04)	1.88 (1.72–2.06)	1.02 (0.97–1.06)	1.19 (1.13–1.25)	1.18 (1.12–1.25)	1.02 (0.97–1.06)	1.19 (1.13–1.25)	1.20 (1.14–1.27)
NSAID or AAP	0.97 (0.87–1.08)	1.02 (0.92–1.14)	1.04 (0.92–1.18)	1.12 (0.96–1.30)	1.11 (0.95–1.29)	1.15 (0.98–1.35)	1.14 (1.07–1.22)	1.16 (1.08–1.24)	1.14 (1.06–1.23)	1.14 (1.09–1.20)	1.15 (1.10–1.20)	1.17 (1.12–1.23)
Interaction	-	-	0.93 (0.71–1.21)	-	-	0.77 (0.48–1.23)	-	-	1.11 (0.92–1.33)	-	-	0.87 (0.75–0.99)
Hypertension												

	2,693 events						32,083 events					
VEGF	16.2 (14.7–17.8)	2.67 (2.35–3.02)	2.76 (2.43–3.14)	16.2 (14.7–17.0)	2.66 (2.35–3.02)	2.76 (2.43–3.13)	6.64 (6.49–6.79)	4.50 (4.36–4.64)	4.53 (4.39–4.68)	6.64 (6.49–6.79)	4.49 (4.35–4.63)	4.6 (4.45–4.75)
NSAID or AAP	0.68 (0.57–0.81)	0.62 (0.52–0.74)	1.00 (0.72–1.39)	0.65 (0.50–0.85)	0.87 (0.66–1.14)	1.72 (1.18–2.51)	1.15 (1.08–1.21)	1.12 (1.06–1.19)	1.21 (1.12–1.30)	1.16 (1.12–1.21)	1.21 (1.16–1.26)	1.37 (1.30–1.44)
Interaction	-	-	0.54 (0.36–0.79)	-	-	0.32 (0.19–0.55)	-	-	0.85 (0.76–0.95)	-	-	0.76 (0.70–0.82)
Proteinuria												
	2,145 events						5,094 events					
VEGF	29.6 (26.0–33.6)	2.38 (2.03–2.80)	2.48 (2.21–2.92)	29.6 (26.0–33.6)	2.38 (2.03–2.80)	2.42 (2.06–2.85)	15.3 (14.4–16.3)	13.6 (12.5–14.7)	14.0 (12.9–15.1)	15.3 (14.4–16.3)	13.6 (12.5–14.7)	14.1 (13.0–15.3)
NSAID or AAP	0.45 (0.33–0.55)	0.43 (0.33–0.55)	0.87 (0.53–1.43)	0.47 (0.33–0.67)	0.73 (0.51–1.04)	1.19 (0.63–2.24)	0.95 (0.82–1.10)	0.95 (0.82–1.11)	1.48 (1.17–1.87)	0.93 (0.83–1.03)	1.02 (0.92–1.14)	1.41 (1.19–1.66)
Interaction	-	-	0.42 (0.24–0.74)	-	-	0.52 (0.24–1.12)	-	-	0.51 (0.37–0.69)	-	-	0.61 (0.49–0.76)

Odds ratio (95% CI). aOR Interaction means logistic regression models including interaction terms. cOR: crude odds ratio, aOR: adjusted odds ratio, VEGF: vascular endothelial growth factor, NSAID: non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug, AAP: acetaminophen